

Polarography of Cerium-N, N-Dihydroxyethylglycine Complexes*

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Polarographic behaviour of Ce(IV) and Ce(III) has been studied in alkaline N, N-dihydroxyethylglycine. The complexes formed with both the oxidation states of cerium are quite stable even at high pH. The complex species formed with both Ce(IV) and Ce(III) are the same and no change in half-wave potentials is noted on changing the ligand concentration. The half-wave potential is very much pH dependent and the studies have been made at 0.2M to 1.0M hydroxyl ion concentrations. The waves, both cathodic and anodic, are fully reversible and are diffusion controlled. Three electrode reactions have been proposed depending upon the hydroxyl ion concentrations.

IN a polarographic study of cerium Noddack and Bruekl¹ found two waves in which $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ of the second wave was $-1.97V$ vs. S.C.E. corresponding to the reduction of Ce(III) to metal². A study of Ce(IV) in KSCN has been made by Meites and coworkers³ and Kapoor and Agarwal^{4,5}. The latter have found the intermediate formation of thiocyanogen free radical as well its polymer. Dolezal and Novak⁶ have observed well defined reversible waves both with Ce(IV) and Ce(III) in potassium carbonate and have suggested the presence of carbonate complexes of both species. The polarographic study of Ce(IV) in lithium sulphate medium was done by Kapoor and Agarwal⁷. Potentiometric studies of Ce(IV) and Ce(III) with N, N-dihydroxyethylglycine have been done by the authors⁸.

The authors in the present communication have done the polarographic study of Ce(IV) and Ce(III) in alkaline N, N-dihydroxyethylglycine (DHEG).

Materials and Methods

All the chemicals used were of Analar grade. The stock solutions of Ce(IV) and Ce(III) were standardized volumetrically⁹. Pure nitrogen supplied in cylinders was further purified by passing it through vanadous sulphate solution¹⁰. Sodium hydroxide free from carbonate was prepared as described by Clark¹¹. Mercury used in D.M.E. was purified as given by Meites¹².

All polarograms were obtained with a automatic photorecording polarograph (Polarograph, System-Heyrovsky, LP-55A). For analysis of polarograms, rising sections of the curves were obtained manually (Toshniwal's polarograph).

The potentials were measured against the saturated calomel electrode which was connected to the solution in the polarographic cell through a salt bridge of potassium chloride. All experiments were carried out by keeping the cell-assembly in a thermostat maintained at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}C$.

Results and Discussion

It was observed that no wave, either cathodic or anodic was obtained unless the pH of the solution was >12 . The wave was illdefined during beginning and remained so till 0.2M NaOH was added. As the accurate measurement of this high pH was not possible, all the observations have been reported in terms of hydroxyl ion concentration. As the ligand contained an acidic hydrogen, its sodium salt was prepared and used in all the experiments.

It was observed that both Ce(IV) and Ce(III) formed stable complexes with DHEG as no precipitation occurred on long keeping in high alkalinity. It was, however, observed that Ce(III)-DHEG complex was oxidised by atmospheric oxygen. The anodic wave of Ce(III) observed in the absence of air became anodic-cathodic on exposure to air and finally became totally cathodic (Figure 1).

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FIGURE -1

Fig. 1. Air Oxidation of Ce(III) in presence of DHEG.

Curve (A) in inert atmosphere, Curve (B) after exposure to air for 1 min., (C) 2 min., (d) 3 min., (E) 4 min. and (F) 5 min.

[Ce(III)]= 5×10^{-4} M, [DHEG]= 3×10^{-1} M
[OH⁻]= 1×10^{-1} M.

Contrary to the general behaviour of a metal ion in the presence of a ligand no shift in the values of half-wave potentials was observed as the concentration of ligand was increased (Table-1).

TABLE 1

$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ of Ce(IV) and Ce(III) in DHEG

[Ce(IV)]= 5×10^{-4} M [Ce(III)]= 5×10^{-4} M
[OH⁻]=0.2M

Temperature= 30 ± 0.1 °C

[DHEG] M	Ratio of DHEG/ Metal	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (in volts vs. S.C.E.)	
		Ce(IV)	Ce(III)
0.10	200	-0.354	-0.355
0.15	300	-0.356	-0.356
0.20	400	-0.355	-0.356
0.30	600	-0.356	-0.354
0.40	800	-0.358	-0.355
0.50	1000	-0.358	-0.356

The plots of $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ vs. E gave straight lines in all the cases and the average slope was found to be $0.062V \pm 0.004V$. Thus the reduction of Ce(IV) to Ce(III) as well as oxidation of Ce(III) to Ce(IV) in this medium appeared to be reversible at D.M.E. and corresponded to one-electron change.

The waves were found to be diffusion controlled in both the oxidation states of cerium in all the cases.

The half-wave potentials of both Ce(IV) and Ce(III) in presence of DHEG were very much pH dependent. The study made of half-wave potentials of Ce(IV) as a function of hydroxyl ion concentration is included in figure 2. Similar results were obtained when study was done with Ce(III). The values of half-wave potentials of both Ce(IV) and Ce(III) at a particular hydroxyl ion concentration were found almost identical showing the system to be fully reversible.

FIGURE -2

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log [OH^-]$ vs. E of Ce(III) and Ce(IV) in DHEG.

[Ce(IV)]= 5×10^{-4} M, [Ce(III)]= 5×10^{-4} M
[DHEG]= 2×10^{-1} M.

No change in the value of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ at a particular hydroxyl ion concentration when ligand concentration was varied extensively (see Table 1) may be due to the fact that both Ce(IV) and Ce(III) complexes have the same number of DHEG units attached to the respective metal atom.

Further the pH-potential studies¹³ have shown that beyond pH 8 the percentage of 1:3 Ce-ligand complex species [both Ce(IV) and Ce(III)] was almost 100% at total cerium concentration 1×10^{-3} M and DHEG concentration 1×10^{-2} M. In the case under

investigation the concentration of cerium was $5 \times 10^{-4}M$ and concentration of DHEG was $0.1M$. It may, therefore, be safely assumed that the predominant species would be 1:3 in both the cases. The electrode reaction may be expressed as

where X may refer to other groups like OH^- etc. Also the net charges on the concerned species have been ignored.

The value of $(m-k)$ obtained from the plot between $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and $\log [\text{OH}^-]$ (Figure 2) was 12 for hydroxyl ion concentrations from $0.2M$ to $0.26M$; 2 for hydroxyl ion concentrations in between $0.26M$ and $0.6M$ and this value was 1 for hydroxyl ion concentrations ranging from $0.6M$ and $1.0M$. The following electrode reactions are, therefore, proposed :

At $[\text{OH}^-]$ from $0.20M$ to $0.26M$

At $[\text{OH}^-]$ from $0.26M$ to $0.6M$

At $[\text{OH}^-]$ from $0.6M$ to $1.0M$

It is, however, not possible to know precisely the actual number of hydroxyl ions attached to the species at this stage.

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